

Education Quarterly Reviews

Demir, Ü. (2022). Students' Metaphorical Perceptions Regarding the Concept of School, School Satisfaction Levels and Elements Affecting Satisfaction. *Education Quarterly Reviews*, Vol.5 Special Issue 2: Current Education Research in Turkey, 511-525.

ISSN 2621-5799

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1993.05.04.640

The online version of this article can be found at:

<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

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Students' Metaphorical Perceptions Regarding the Concept of School, School Satisfaction Levels and Elements Affecting Satisfaction

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Abstract

In the contemporary education approach, the concepts of satisfaction, teamwork and motivation of school stakeholders, especially the concept of satisfaction are considered important along with approaches such as Human Resources Management, Effective School and Total Quality Management. If it is accepted that the student is at the center of the elements of the school, student satisfaction comes to the fore. The aim of this research is to determine students' perceptions of school through metaphors, to reveal their school satisfaction levels according to some variables and to offer suggestions for increasing satisfaction. The research is mixed method and in the quantitative part, the Students' School Satisfaction Scale (SMSQ) developed by the researcher was applied to the students studying at high schools in Antalya. In the qualitative part, face-to-face interviews were conducted with the students by using a semi-structured interview form prepared by the researcher, and their views on the metaphorical perceptions of the school and the factors affecting their school satisfaction were taken. In the results of the research, it was seen that while the general satisfaction of the students according to the dimensions of the school was moderately satisfied. According to their gender and grade levels, it was determined that there was a significant difference between the groups. The metaphors produced by the students about the school and their reasons are classified and the factors affecting their satisfaction with the school are included.

Keywords: Student, School, Satisfaction, Perception, Metaphor

1. Introduction

Management is defined as the effective and efficient use of human and material resources in line with organizational goals (Aydın, 1991). When the development of management science is examined, it is seen that the concepts of performance, production and organization that make up the Classical period are the priority targets, while in the Neoclassical period, human resources and relations are balanced with the human dimension-organization dimension and started to be considered as a way to increase the performance of the organization. Along with the contemporary management approaches after the neoclassical period, Human Resources Management (HRM) and the human element of the organization have started to be mentioned more in recent years. This has brought employee satisfaction to the forefront, as well as concepts such as job satisfaction, morale and motivation, especially in the organization. Contemporary management approaches in general and Total Quality

Management (TQM) and HRM in particular focus on the satisfaction of the human element in the organization today. The understanding of TQM proposes to evaluate students as a whole, to ensure the participation of teachers and students in school management, and to empower them more.

Giving students points according to their course success is seen as a reflection of the classical management approach. Schools that implement Deming's philosophy of quality have a school culture based on mutual respect and trust, rather than fear and doubt. Schools have an organizational culture where all students, teachers, administrators and support staff work happily (Çetinkaya & Gülmez, 2002). Happiness is the state of being proud of achieving all aspirations completely and continuously; satisfaction is also defined as a person feels when buying a good or service that she/he wants or needs to receive or perform (Shee and Wang, 2008; Cobuild English Dictionary, 1999; Turkish Language Association, 2019). In this case, schools are expected to be environments where students feel happy and will be satisfied with the physical and administrative services that schools offer them. Because schools are institutions that are prepared to realize the educational goals of students. The raw material on which he works is the human coming from the society and going to the society. Mou et al., (2007) define teaching as a service sector and students as customers of the service provided. Therefore, customers in the education and training sector can be counted as students. Student satisfaction is generally accepted as a short-term attitude resulting from the evaluation of the student's educational experience. When actual performance meets or exceeds student expectations, student satisfaction results (Elliott & Healy, 2001).

1.1 Factors affecting school satisfaction

The satisfaction of the student towards the institution where he/she studied is basically a multidimensional phenomenon. This phenomenon can be examined with an approach that includes different dimensions such as the quality of education, physical spaces, application opportunities, social, cultural and sportive opportunities, and the individual characteristics of the student (Uzgören & Uzgören, 2007). Some of the factors affecting student satisfaction are; Academic factors include the quality of education, in-class and out-of-class communication with students, course curriculum, books and other materials to be used in lessons. It is thought that the positive or negative emotions students feel in their schools will affect many factors from their attitudes towards school, their success, their commitment to school, their attendance to school, their communication skills at school and in the classroom, and their general perceptions about the school. Likewise, these factors play a decisive role in the formation of students' perceptions of satisfaction or dissatisfaction with their school.

There are many studies in the literature examining student satisfaction and the factors affecting satisfaction. The findings of some of these studies are as follows; In Barker and Gump (1964) study, it was determined that small schools (100-150 people) offer more opportunities to their students than large schools with more than 2000 people. In these schools, students have more chance to take part in various activities and play leadership roles. The architecture of school buildings, indoor social space, activity areas is effective in the success, morale and behavior of students. The availability of flexible and adaptable spaces, larger rooms and areas for students' art and social activities at the school play an important role in making the school a learning environment (Özbayraktar, 2005; Aksu, Demirel, & Bektaş, 2011; Karakuş, 2010; Kıldan, 2007). Factors such as school staff's interest in students' learning, teacher support, friendly approach of teachers and active and authentic learning seem to be positively related to student satisfaction (Şahin, 2007; Ward, 1995).

In the study named Sop (2020) Education-Teaching Satisfaction, Academic Procrastination Tendency and Academic Achievement Relationship, students' school satisfaction and academic achievement levels were compared and it was determined that satisfaction statistically significantly reduced students' academic procrastination and increased academic success.

In their research, Atay and Yıldırım (2008) used five satisfaction sub-dimensions: the adequacy of the educational environment, school-student relationship, social, cultural and scientific activities, the effectiveness of the Internet

in communication, and the effectiveness of foreign language lessons. As a common result of the research, it reveals the fact that the decrease in the school satisfaction levels of the students paves the way for the emergence of behaviors such as absenteeism and truancy, showing undesirable behaviors in the classroom, and not being willing to do the assigned tasks.

1.2 Metaphors as a means for determining school satisfaction

Metaphors that help in conceptualizing perceptions and revealing concrete pictures about these perceptions help convey information, take legitimate actions, set goals, and structure systems in a coherent way (Goglar, Gross, Hartman, & Cunliffe, 2008). Likewise, it is thought that one of the most effective ways of obtaining information about schools and understanding the school structure is to determine student perceptions, which are considered an important stakeholder. From this point of view, it can be seen that metaphors are powerful tools in understanding schools or revealing the value given to them and the perception felt.

When the literature is examined, there are many metaphor studies related to school. While some of the metaphors in these studies are negative metaphors such as prison, circus, army, factory, zoo; positive metaphors such as family, home, information center, shopping center, orchard were also identified (Inbar, 1996; Mahlios & Maxson, 1998; Saban, 2008; Powell, Farrar & Cohen, 1985; Balcı, 1999; Özdemir, 2012). ; Özdemir and Akkaya, 2013).

Demir (2007) revealed that Turkish and American secondary school students' perceptions of school differ according to culture. While half of the Turkish participants perceived the school as a "home", the other part perceived the school as a "care place", "psychological feeding place", "educational example". While some of the American participants perceived the school as "wild, crowded, complex, boring, painful, orderly environment in which students have to learn to survive", some of them perceived school as "a place of fun, care, interest and learning". In Özdemir and Akkaya's (2013) study, it was determined that students and teachers felt blocked, limited, and thought that they were kept under surveillance and control. It was revealed that the students mostly used the metaphor of prison.

The aim of this research is to reveal high school students' perceptions of school through metaphors and to determine their level of satisfaction with school according to some demographic variables of the students. Another aim of the research is to determine the factors that increase and decrease the students' school satisfaction and to make scientific suggestions for increasing satisfaction. In the light of these aims, answers to the following questions were sought:

- 1a) What is the school satisfaction level of high school students according to the types of high schools they study?
- 1b) What is the school satisfaction level of high school students according to their grade level and is there a significant difference between these levels?
- 1c) What is the school satisfaction level of high school students according to the gender of the students and is there a significant difference between these levels?
- 2) What are the metaphors produced by high school students about school and their reasons for these metaphors?
- 3) According to the opinions of high school students, what are the factors that increase or decrease school satisfaction?

2. Method

In this section, explanations about the research model, study group, data collection technique, and data analysis are given.

2.1 The Research Model

In the study, a mixed pattern method was followed by using quantitative and qualitative research methods together. Mixed methods research is defined as the researcher combining qualitative and quantitative methods, approaches and concepts within a study or successive studies (Creswell, 2003; Tashakkori & Teddlie, 1998; Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004). The quantitative part of the research is the survey model; the qualitative part was prepared in a phenomenological pattern.

2.2 Study Group

The study group of the quantitative part of the study consists of 36 official Anatolian high schools, 27 vocational high schools, 3 science high schools and 9 Imam Hatip high schools in Konyaalti, Kepez, Muratpasa, Aksu and Dosemealti districts in Antalya province in the 2020-2021 academic year. The schools included in the study were selected in accordance with the easily accessible disproportionate cluster sampling. In the selection of the students, the random method was used by taking a certain number of (5 each) students from each grade level (9-10-11-12) selected by stratified sampling method from each high school type. Thus, a total of 920 students, 20 from each high school sampled, were sent a questionnaire, but a total of 725 questionnaires were taken into consideration, some of which were excluded because they contained missing data or were in extreme values, and it was determined that the sample represented the population at the .05 error level (Balci, 2009; Krejcie & Morgan, 1970).

In the qualitative part of the research, in the selection of the schools to be interviewed, a total of 20 students from 5 Anatolian high schools in regions with different socioeconomic structures as much as possible and a certain number of each grade level of these high schools were selected according to the maximum diversity sampling method from purposive sampling methods. It was decided by the researcher to conduct the qualitative part of the study based on interviews in this type of high school, both in terms of Anatolian high schools being the type of high school with the lowest satisfaction levels as a result of the survey application, and being the most common among the high school types (MEB, 2020) participating in the study.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Students Participating in the Study

Variable		N (725)	%
Gender	Female	387	53
	Male	338	47
Grade Level	9th	205	29
	10th	231	31
	11th	182	26
	12th	107	14
School (High School)Type	Imam Hatip	109	15
	Vocational	168	23
	Anatolian	306	42
	Science	142	20
School Size (Population)	less than 500	173	24
	more than 500	552	76

When the demographic characteristics of the participants are examined, it is understood that 387 of the 725 students studying in all high school types are female and 338 are male. When high school types are evaluated, it is seen that 109 of them are in imam hatip high schools, 168 in vocational high schools, 306 in Anatolian high schools and 142 students in science high schools; when examined in terms of grade levels, the 9th grade level is 205; 231 at the 10th grade level; It is seen that 182 students at the 11th grade level and 107 students at the 12th grade level

participated. In terms of the size of the school, it was determined that there were 173 students in high schools with less than 500 students and 552 students in high schools with more than 500 students.

Table 2: Demographic Characteristics of Anatolian High School Students Who Participated in the Qualitative Part of the Study

Variable		N (20)	%
Gender	Female	11	51
	Male	9	49
Grade Level	9th	5	25
	10th	5	25
	11th	5	25
	12th	5	25

When the demographic characteristics of the participants who were interviewed in the qualitative part of the research are examined, it is understood that 11 of the 20 students studying in Anatolian high school are female and 9 are male. In terms of grade levels, it is seen that 5 students from each level (9-10-11 and 12th grade) participated in equal numbers.

2.3 Data Collection and Analysis

In the quantitative part of this thesis, the “Student Satisfaction with School Scale” (SMS) developed by the researcher was applied to measure the satisfaction levels of the students studying at official high schools in Antalya. In the qualitative part, a semi-structured interview form prepared by the researcher and consisting of open-ended questions was used.

Quantitative part of the study;

In this study, the Students' School Satisfaction Scale (SMS) developed by the researcher regarding the main problem and consisting of six dimensions (*Administrative Structure and Functioning of the School, Relevance of Course Content, Program and Curriculum, Physical Structure of the School, Adequacy of Gardens and Departments, The Quality of Education at School and Its Contribution to Student Development, Services and Opportunities Provided by the School to the Students, Student-Teacher Relations and Communication*) was delivered to 800 students studying at public high schools in five central districts of Antalya in the 2020-2021 academic year. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett tests were conducted to test the analysis suitability on the data set of 725 students, which was obtained after the detection of missing data that would not be included in the analysis. As a result of the KMO and Bartlett Tests (KMO = .96, Bartlett's Test of Sphericity= 7148,385 df=902, $p = .000$), it was determined that the data were suitable for factor analysis (KMO $\geq$ 0.70 and $p < .05$) (Pallant, 2016; Hutcheson and Sofroniou, 1999; Seer, 2015). SPSS package program was used to analyze the data obtained from the students. While the t-test was used to compare the arithmetic mean, frequency, item analysis, and the mean of two independent groups, One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were used to compare the mean of more than two groups, and the LSD test, one of the Post-Hoc tests, was used to determine between which groups the difference was. The level of significance in statistical procedures was accepted as .05.

Qualitative part of the study;

Face-to-face interviews were conducted with 20 students from all grade levels from Anatolian high schools, using a semi-structured interview form consisting of open-ended questions prepared by the researcher in order to make an in-depth analysis of the metaphors they produced about the school and the factors affecting school satisfaction

in line with the school satisfaction levels obtained from the students as a result of the survey. Content analysis was used in the analysis of the data obtained from the interview recordings. In addition, codes such as FS11-7, MS10-2 were used for the participants in order to hide the personal identities of the participants during the data analysis process. This research was carried out on a voluntary basis by personally visiting the schools determined by the researcher. At the same time, the research process is written clearly from start to finish, making it possible to re-apply it by other researchers. The reliability of the research was calculated by using Miles and Huberman's [Reliability: Consensus / (Consensus + Disagreement)] formula (Cited by Saban, 2008). In qualitative research, the desired reliability is provided when the agreement between the evaluation of the experts and the researcher is 90% or more (Saban, 2008). According to Miles and Huberman's formula, the reliability of the study was calculated as 0.94.

3. Findings

1a. Findings Related to the Satisfaction Levels of the Students according to the High School Types

The satisfaction perceptions of the students participating in the research in terms of high school types (Imam Hatip-Vocational-Anatolian-Science High School) are given and presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Distribution of Students' Satisfaction Levels by High School Types and ANOVA Test Results

Dimensions	School Type	N	$\bar{X}$	S	F	p	Difference (LSD)
Administrative Structure and Functioning of the School	<i>ImamHatip (a)</i>	109	3.56	.93	1.23	.296	
	<i>Vocational (b)</i>	168	3.52	.95			
	<i>Anatolian (c)</i>	306	3.52	.99			
	<i>Science (d)</i>	142	3.70	.90			
	<i>total</i>	725	3.56	.96			
Relevance of Course Content, Program and Curriculum	<i>ImamHatip (a)</i>	109	3.32	.97	3.72	.011*	a-b
	<i>Vocational (b)</i>	168	3.34	.94			a-c
	<i>Anatolian (c)</i>	306	3.10	.95			a-d
	<i>Science (d)</i>	142	3.07	.93			b-c
	<i>total</i>	725	3.18	.95			b-d
Physical Structure of the School, Adequacy of Gardens and Departments	<i>ImamHatip (a)</i>	109	3.65	.77	14.38	.000*	a-b
	<i>Vocational (b)</i>	168	3.25	.89			a-c
	<i>Anatolian (c)</i>	306	3.31	.86			b-d
	<i>Science (d)</i>	142	3.74	.67			c-d
	<i>total</i>	725	3.43	.84			
The Quality of Education at School and Its Contribution to Student Development	<i>ImamHatip (a)</i>	109	3.70	.95	2.89	.035*	a-c
	<i>Vocational (b)</i>	168	3.54	.98			
	<i>Anatolian (c)</i>	306	3.40	1.00			
	<i>Science (d)</i>	142	3.49	.88			
	<i>total</i>	725	3.49	.97			
Services and Opportunities Provided by the School to the Students	<i>ImamHatip (a)</i>	109	3.70	.80	5.96	.001*	b-d
	<i>Vocational (b)</i>	168	3.52	.89			c-d
	<i>Anatolian (c)</i>	306	3.61	.84			
	<i>Science (d)</i>	142	3.89	.61			
	<i>total</i>	725	3.66	.82			
Student-Teacher Relations and Communication	<i>ImamHatip (a)</i>	109	3.83	1.01	1.19	.310	
	<i>Vocational (b)</i>	168	3.65	.99			
	<i>Anatolian (c)</i>	306	3.65	.90			
	<i>Science (d)</i>	142	3.67	.85			
	<i>total</i>	725	3.68	.93			

Total	ImamHatip (a)	109	3.49	.75	2.05	.105
(General Satisfaction)	Vocational (b)	168	3.38	.80		
	Anatolian (c)	306	3.32	.78		
	Science (d)	142	3.47	.65		
	total	725	3.39	.76		

*p<0.5

When the results of the ANOVA Test conducted regarding the satisfaction perceptions of the students according to the high school types they study are examined, it is seen that there is a significant difference between the students' satisfaction with the school and the high school types. LSD, one of the Post-Hoc tests, was used to determine which groups were different according to high school types, and the arithmetic averages of these groups were examined. When we look at all the dimensions of the school in the table, it is understood that the school satisfaction level of the students in imam hatip high schools is higher than the students in other high school types. When examined in terms of dimensions, the satisfaction level of science high school students in the Administrative Structure and Functioning of the School is $\bar{x}=3.70$; it has been determined that the satisfaction levels of Anatolian high school and vocational high school students have the lowest satisfaction as $\bar{x}=3.52$. While the satisfaction perceptions of the vocational high school students, who are higher than the other high school types in terms of Relevance of Course Content, Program and Curriculum, are $\bar{x}=3.34$, it is seen that the average of science high school students has the lowest perception of satisfaction as $\bar{x}=3.07$.

It was found that the satisfaction perceptions of science high school students ($\bar{x}=3.74/3.89$) in the dimensions of the Physical Structure of the School, the Adequacy of Gardens and Departments, and the Opportunities and Services Provided by the School to the Students ($\bar{x}=3.74/3.89$) have the highest degree among high school types; it is observed that vocational high school students' satisfaction with this dimension is at the lowest level ($\bar{x}=3.25/3.52$).

In dimensions of Quality of Education and Its Contribution to Student Development and Student-Teacher Relationship and Communication at School, imam hatip high school has the highest level of school satisfaction ($\bar{x}=3.70/3.83$); the type with the lowest satisfaction was found to be vocational high school students ($\bar{x}=3.52/3.32$).

1b. Findings Regarding Grade Levels of Satisfaction of Students in High Schools

The satisfaction perceptions of the high school students participating in the research in terms of grade levels (9th-10th-11th-12th grades) are included and are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Distribution of Students' Satisfaction Levels by Class Levels and ANOVA Test Results

Dimensions	Grade Level	N	$\bar{X}$	S	F	p	Difference (LSD)
Administrative Structure and Functioning of the School	9th (a)	205	3.78	.85	10,25	.000*	a-c
	10th (b)	231	3.61	.95			a-d
	11thf(c)	182	3.45	.96			b-d
	12th(d)	107	3.19	1.03			c-d
	total	725	3.56	.96			
Relevance of Course Content, Program and Curriculum	9th (a)	205	3.28	.93	2,78	.040*	a-d
	10th (b)	231	3.19	.96			b-d
	11thf(c)	182	3.20	.97			c-a
	12th(d)	107	2.96	.93			c-d
	total	725	3.18	.95			
Physical Structure of the School, Adequacy of Gardens and Departments	9th (a)	205	3.56	.82	8.94	.000*	a-c
	10th (b)	231	3.54	.80			a-d
	11thf(c)	182	3.36	.87			b-c
	12th(d)	107	3.10	.84			b-d

	<i>total</i>	725	3.43	.84			c-d
The Quality of Education at School and Its Contribution to Student Development	<i>9th (a)</i>	205	3.63	.91	5.57	.001*	a-c
	<i>10th (b)</i>	231	3.57	.93			a-d
	<i>11thf(c)</i>	182	3.42	1.00			b-a
	<i>12th(d)</i>	107	3.20	1.03			b-d
	<i>total</i>	725	3.49	.97			
Services and Opportunities Provided by the School to the Students	<i>9th (a)</i>	205	3.89	.73	19.25	.000*	a-c
	<i>10th (b)</i>	231	3.71	.78			a-d
	<i>11thf(c)</i>	182	3.61	.80			b-a
	<i>12th(d)</i>	107	3.19	.89			b-d
	<i>total</i>	725	3.66	.82			c-d
Student-Teacher Relations and Communication	<i>9th (a)</i>	205	3.68	.94	1.93	.123	
	<i>10th (b)</i>	231	3.77	.90			
	<i>11thf(c)</i>	182	3.67	.94			
	<i>12th(d)</i>	107	3.50	.99			
	<i>total</i>	725	3.68	.93			
Total (General Satisfaction)	<i>9th (a)</i>	205	3.54	.71	9.16	.000*	a-c
	<i>10th (b)</i>	231	3.44	.74			a-d
	<i>11thf(c)</i>	182	3.34	.77			b-c
	<i>12th(d)</i>	107	3.09	.78			b-d
	<i>total</i>	725	3.39	.76			

* $p < 0.5$

When the results of the ANOVA Test conducted regarding the satisfaction perceptions of the students in Table 4 according to the grade level they are studying are examined, it is seen that there is a significant difference between the grade levels of the students' satisfaction with the school. The LSD test, one of the Post-Hoc tests, was used to find the source of the difference as a result of the analysis of variance. Accordingly, since $P = .00$ ($p < .05$), there is a significant difference at the level of .05 between the satisfaction levels of the students studying in high schools according to their grade levels. When we look at all the dimensions of the school, it is understood that the satisfaction levels of the students studying in the 9th grade are higher than the students at other grade levels. In the Administrative Structure and Functioning of the School dimension, the satisfaction level of the 9th grade students was $\bar{x} = 3.78$, while the average of the 12th grade students in the same dimension was $\bar{x} = 3.19$, and it was determined that the satisfaction decreased as the grade levels increased.

In dimension of the relevance of the course content, program and curriculum, the satisfaction perception of the 9th grade students is $\bar{x} = 3.28$, while the average of the 12th grade students is $\bar{x} = 2.96$. Again, in terms of the physical structure of the school, the adequacy of the garden and its departments, the satisfaction level of the 9th grade students is $\bar{x} = 3.56$, while the level of satisfaction decreases to the $\bar{x} = 3.36 / \bar{x} = 3.10$ band at the 11th and 12th grades as the grade levels increase. And finally, in parallel with the other results in the dimension of the Services and Opportunities Provided by the School to the Students, it is seen that the satisfaction levels of the 9th grade students are relatively high. Accordingly, while the satisfaction level of the 9th grade students was $\bar{x} = 3.89$, it was determined that the satisfaction level of the 12th grade students decreased to $\bar{x} = 3.19$; no significant difference was found in students' perceptions of school satisfaction according to their grade levels in the dimension of Student-Teacher Relationship and Communication.

1c. Findings Related to Satisfaction Levels of High School Students by Gender

In this section, the satisfaction levels of the high school students participating in the research in terms of gender are included and are presented in Table 5:

Table 5: Distribution of Students' Satisfaction Levels by Gender and t-Test Results

Dimensions	Gender	N	$\bar{x}$	S	sd	t	p
Administrative Structure and Functioning of the School	F	387	3.51	.98	723	1.52	.128
	M	338	3.61	.93			
Relevance of Course Content, Program and Curriculum	F	387	3.08	.91	723	3.15	.002*
	M	338	3.30	.99			
Physical Structure of the School, Adequacy of Gardens and Departments	F	387	3.43	.85	723	.070	.945
	M	338	3.44	.84			
The Quality of Education at School and Its Contribution to Student Development	F	387	3.43	.98	723	1.96	.050*
	M	338	3.57	.95			
Services and Opportunities Provided by the School to the Students	F	387	3.62	.83	723	1.17	.240
	M	338	3.70	.80			
Student-Teacher Relations and Communication	F	387	3.63	.95	723	1.61	.108
	M	338	3.74	.92			
Total	F	387	3.33	.75	723	2.12	.034*
	M	338	3.45	.76			

*p<0.5

The distribution of the satisfaction levels of the students studying in high schools according to the gender of the students and the results of the “t” test are seen. Accordingly, it is understood that 387 of the 725 students participating in the research are female students and 338 are male students. When the students are examined in general, the arithmetic mean of the satisfaction levels of the female students is $\bar{x}=3.33$. The arithmetic mean of male students' satisfaction levels is $\bar{x}=3.45$. In the statistical analysis, the "t" value is 2.12. The “p” value regarding the satisfaction levels of high school students is $p=.03$ and $p<.05$. For this reason, it is seen that there is a significant difference between the students according to the gender variable regarding the satisfaction levels. It is understood when we look at the arithmetic averages of which group of students' satisfaction level is low or high according to the gender variable. Accordingly, it is seen that male students' satisfaction levels from school in all dimensions are higher than female students. While the lowest level of satisfaction with the school, which students (female-male) meet in common, is in the dimension of Adequacy of Course Content, Program and Curriculum; ($\bar{x}=3.08/3.30$) and it was determined that the highest satisfaction perceptions were in the dimension of Student-Teacher Relationship and Communication at School ($\bar{x}= 3.63/3.74$).

2. Opinions of High School Students on Metaphors They Produced About School and Their Reasons

In this section, the opinions of the high school students participating in the research on the metaphors they produced about the school and their reasons are given and presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Metaphors and Reasons of High School Students Regarding School

	Metaphors	Reasons	Participations	f
METAPHORS (POSITIVE)	Tree	Challenging; but the result is satisfactory.	<i>FS11-2, FS12-12</i>	2
	Football field	The tree is rooted and useful, but yields results depending on your approach to it. For me, it means the place where I miss the classes and play football all day long.	<i>MS11-4</i>	1
	A disciplined place that prepares you for the future.	Because it makes us professionals.	<i>MS11-5</i>	1
	Fun vehicle	I see it as a means to reach my goals.	<i>FS12-5</i>	1
	Second home	It's not boarding, but we spend more time here than at home.	<i>MS10-6</i>	1
	Home	School is a very special place, in my opinion.	<i>FS10-7</i>	1
	METAPHORS (NEGATIVE)	Spinach	I have to eat even though I don't like it.	<i>FS9-1</i>
Jelly beans		It makes you nauseous when you eat too much.	<i>MS10-1</i>	1
Semi-open prison		Entry and exit with permission. The school manager is like the prison warden.	<i>MS12-2</i>	1
The Military		It's not like a prison, but a purposeful community with lots of rules and no fun.	<i>FS12-3</i>	1
Prison, Educational Prison, Children's Prison		A place that acts at the request of the administrator and can be entered and exited with permission. Same with their sentries, their walls, and the fact that we're being questioned. Our communication with the outside is cut off; We just have to talk to the people at school. The same in terms of operation; The only difference is that we are training here.	<i>FS10-4, MS9-3, FS9-9, FS12-8, MS11-7</i>	5

Metaphors	Reasons	Participations	f
	We stay with our peers for a long time without leaving school.		
Farm Sheep Flock (Students)	The best fed animals on farms are taken to slaughter; Our most successful ones also benefit from school, but it is wasted.	FS11-6	1
Labyrinth	It is a very complex and difficult to understand structure in terms of the courses and the people in it.	FS9-11	1
Office	Employees are stuck there all day.	MS9-8	1
Closed Box	Even if we want to go out, we cannot go out without permission.	MS10-9	1

When the metaphors produced by high school students about school and their reasons are examined, it is seen that metaphors are divided into metaphors with positive meaning and metaphors with negative meaning. When school metaphors were examined, it was determined that metaphors with negative meanings were more than positive ones. Two of the students (FS11-2, FS12-12) made a tree analogy to the school; 5 students (FS10-4, MS9-3, FS9-9, FS12-8, MS11-7) used metaphors such as Prison, Education Prison and Children's Prison. Again in the table, the school of one of the participating students (KFS11-6) is on the farm; the students at the school to the flock of sheep; another participant student (FS9-11) used the metaphor of the labyrinth to compare the school to a complex place.

3. High School Students' Views on the Factors Affecting School Satisfaction

The opinions of the high school students who participated in the research on the factors that increase or decrease their school satisfaction are given in Table 7 and Table 8.

Table 7: Factors Increasing School Satisfaction According to High School Students' Views

Factors Increasing School Satisfaction	Participations	f
1. My Friends	MS11-7, FS9-9, FS12-8, FS12-10, MS10-6, MS12-4, MS9-3, MS11-5, MS12-2, MS10-1, FS12-5, FS11-6, FS12-3, MS8-9, MS10-9	15
2. My Favorite Teachers	FS10-7, FS12-8, FS9-11, MS10-6, MS11-4, MS10-1, FS11-6, FS12-5, FS12-3, MS8-9, MS11-7, MS10-9	12
3. My Favorite Lessons	MS12-2, MS12-4, FS9-11, FS11-6, MS10-9	5

When the factors that increase school satisfaction according to the opinions of high school students are examined, it has been determined that the students' opinions mostly focus on three elements and these elements are *My Friends*, *My Favorite Teachers*, *My Favorite Lessons*. According to the table, 15 students gave the most opinion

on the factors that increase their school satisfaction as *My Friends*, followed by 12 students with the answer *My Favorite Teachers* and 5 students in the third place with the answer *My Favorite Lessons*.

Table 8: Factors Reducing School Satisfaction According to High School Students' Opinions

Factors Reducing School Satisfaction	Participations	f
1. Curriculum	FS9-1, FS11-2, FS11-6, FS10-4, MS10-1, FS11-6, FS12-3, FS11-2	8
2. Anxiety for the future	MS11-7, FS9-9, FS12-8, FS9-1, MS8-9, MS10-9, MS11-5	7
3. Weekly course schedule	FS10-7, MS10-6, FS9-1, MS12-2, MS10-1, FS12-3	6

When the factors that reduce school satisfaction according to the opinions of high school students are examined in the table, it has been determined that the students' opinions focus on three elements in particular, and these elements are *Curriculum*, *Anxiety for the future* and *Weekly course schedule*. According to the table, it is seen that 8 students gave the highest number of opinions as *Curriculum* regarding the factors that decrease school satisfaction, 7 students who followed it gave the answer of *Anxiety for the future* and 6 students gave the answer of *Weekly course schedule*.

4. Results and Recommendations

The first sub-problem of the study was prepared as *What is the satisfaction of high school students with regard to their school types, grade level and gender, and is there a significant difference between these levels?* When examined in terms of gender variable, it was determined that there was a significant difference between female students and male students studying at high schools in terms of school satisfaction perception levels, and accordingly, it was seen that female students' school satisfaction levels were lower than male students. When the literature was examined, it was found that the results of the research conducted in which the school satisfaction of female students were higher than that of males (Özdemir, 2012).

When the school satisfaction perception levels of the students were examined according to the high school types they studied, it was seen that there was a significant difference between the high school types. Accordingly, the high school type with a relatively low general satisfaction level (I am moderately satisfied) belongs to the students in Anatolian high schools; It has been determined that the students who have a relatively high (I am satisfied) perception of satisfaction are the students of Imam Hatip High Schools. The result of this research is compatible with the findings of Yılmaz's (2007) study on the quality of school life. When examined in terms of dimensions, it was determined that the difference between the satisfaction perception levels of Anatolian high school students and imam hatip high School students was the highest in the dimensions of the Physical Structure of the School, the Adequacy of the Gardens and Departments, and the Relevance of the Course Content, Program and Curriculum. Some programs and models such as the Educational Guidance and Support Program (EGSP), Teacher Development Program (TDP) and projects such as TUBITAK and Erasmus are carried out in Imam Hatip high schools through the Quality Monitoring System supported by the Ministry of National Education General Directorate of Religious Education. It is thought that it contributes to the physical structure of the students and that the opportunity to improve their physical structure increases the school satisfaction of the students.

According to the study of Kayıkçı, Altun and Karakoç (2019), one of the most important reasons why the physical structures of high schools create dissatisfaction for students is that school areas are not allocated by estimating the number of students in the coming years, taking into account population density due to unplanned schooling, and

often the pre-planned school gardens are additional buildings. This aforementioned research shows parallelism with the result of Anatolian high school students' satisfaction perceptions. Additional buildings to the school garden cause congestion in the pre-planned service areas of the school, as well as narrowing the school gardens and reducing the playgrounds per student, which causes the dissatisfaction of the students. The student's opinion on this situation explains this situation: *"From the outside, the school looks like a boutique hotel; later, another floor was built and the area was tried to be expanded, but the garden area was narrowed; Despite this, our class size is still crowded."* (FS12-2) While one of the most important reasons why the students of Anatolian high schools have a lower level of satisfaction in terms of *Adequacy of Course Content, Program and Curriculum* is that the program range of these high schools is very general and includes different courses in the curriculum; it is thought that the programs of the students in Imam Hatip high schools are more likely to coincide with a certain field. The opinions of the students regarding this situation support the situation: *"I think that some of the course topics do not contribute to me. We learn in detail many content that I believe will not be of use to me in the future. Learning all the courses for a long time creates problems for our academic life and career choice in the future."* (FS9-1) According to the results of the study, it was observed that the school satisfaction perceptions of high school students tended to decrease as their grade levels increased. In other words, it has been determined that the students' level of satisfaction with school in the 9th grade is higher than the other grade levels, while the lowest level of satisfaction belongs to the students in the 12th grade. These findings support the studies of Eccles, Midgley, and Adler (1984) and Özdemir (2012). In the aforementioned studies, it has been determined that student motivation towards school tends to decrease as the grade level rises. Regarding this sub-problem, it is thought that with the increase in grade levels, students' higher education entrance exam triggers anxiety due to the approaching time and this causes a decrease in school satisfaction. The statement of a student (MS12-4) *"If you had had this interview with me two years ago, I would have been much more comfortable and would have answered positively, but right now I have a lot of exam anxiety, the exam is approaching"* explains that exam anxiety plays an important role in satisfaction. In our exam-oriented education system, as the exam date approaches, teachers, school administrators and even parents are affected by it, and this naturally affects the student negatively. It can be said that the school satisfaction of the student who feels himself under pressure decreases indirectly.

When the metaphors produced by high school students about school, which is the second sub-problem of the research, and the reasons for these metaphors are examined, it has been revealed that the metaphors and justifications produced by Anatolian high school students for school are divided into positive and negative metaphors. As a result of the study, it can be stated that the metaphors with positive or negative meanings produced by the students about the school are in parallel with the results of many school metaphor studies in the literature (Saban, 2008; Balcı & Mazlum, 2018; Bülbül & Gökçe-Toker, 2014; Özdemir & Akkaya, 2013). One student (MS10-1) had a feeling of disgust towards the school on the grounds of the *"jelly beans"* metaphor and expressing it, and another student (FS9-1) said the end of Friday, *"I come to school on Fridays motivated; because it is the last day of the week and the weekend reminds me of the days when there is no school."* His expression as the herald (reminder) of the Saturday-Sunday weekend can actually be interpreted as stating that school is a tiring and repulsive factor. Students' use of metaphors such as (FS10-4, MS9-3, FS9-9, FS12-8, MS11-7) *Semi-Open Prison, Prison, Educational Prison, Children's Prison* and *"Entering and exiting with permission. The warden is like the prison warden."* *"It's the same with their sentries, their walls, and our interrogation."* It is thought that this is another way of expressing that students see school as a place where they are stuck or an environment where they are punished. It has been determined that the metaphors produced by the students are in line with the results of the metaphor study of the students' school principals by Şahin and Sabancı (2018). Regarding school metaphors, it was determined that a student (FS9-11) compared the school to a *labyrinth*. The reason for this metaphor is *"It is a very complex and difficult structure in terms of the lessons and the people in it."* It is thought that the school is trying to give a clue about stakeholder relations. Likewise, it is seen that one student (FS11-6) likened the school to the Farm and the students to the Sheep flock. She told as a justification, *"The best fed animals on farms are taken to slaughter; the most successful of us also benefit from school, but it is wasted."* It is thought that she talked about the difficulties in choosing a profession in the education system.

The third sub-problem of the research was prepared as factors that increase or decrease school satisfaction according to the opinions of Anatolian high school students. In the qualitative interviews conducted to find answers

to this sub-problem, the following results were obtained: According to the opinions of the students, it was determined that the factors that increase their school satisfaction were mostly answered as *my friends, my favourite teachers, my favourite lessons*, while the students answered the most as *curriculum, anxiety for future, weekly course schedule* for the factors that decrease school satisfaction. In terms of the dimensions of the school, these views of Anatolian high school students are compatible with the answers of "my favourite teachers", which increases school satisfaction, and the dimension *Student-Teacher Relationship and Communication*, which is determined to be the highest level of satisfaction. Again, one of the results of the research, *Curriculum, Weekly course schedule* answers to the factors that reduce school satisfaction, while the other dimension of the school, *Adequacy of Course Content, Program and Curriculum* has the lowest satisfaction level, which proves that it is in parallel with student opinions.

In the light of the findings, the following recommendations can be made:

- School buildings and gardens should have an aesthetic architectural structure that appeals to the psychology of the students.
- Social, cultural and artistic activities in schools should be increased in order to reduce the uniformity of the learning environment and the pressure of exams.
- Long-term plans should be included in the construction of schools, taking into account the social demographic and population growth.
- Relationships between student satisfaction and school engagement, school attendance and academic achievement variables can be examined.

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